

Groundwater tables amidst climate change in low-lying Beaufort, South Carolina

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Abstract

Increases in the intensity of rainfall and rising sea levels associated with climate change lead to rising coastal groundwater levels and threaten subsurface infrastructure and coastal resilience. To evaluate this threat, fifteen monitoring wells were set up in Beaufort County, South Carolina, where septic systems play a significant role in wastewater treatment. The hydraulic head was recorded every fifteen minutes for 15 months, from May 2022 to August 2023. Pastas Groundwater, which is an open-source Python package that implements a transfer function noise model based on a response function, was used to model the water levels in each well to estimate the risk of groundwater impairment of septic systems over three decades. Tidal and rainfall data were downloaded from Ft. Pulaski and Beaufort Marine Corps Air Station (MCAS), respectively. Model calibration was done using only the first 13 months of field data. Model fits declined significantly when using the full 15 months of data, potentially owing to heavy local rainfall at the MCAS site that did not affect the rest of the field area.

In this study, the results from twelve wells that were not installed directly in tidal creeks are presented. In all but one of these wells, the water level rose significantly by about 1 m during a period of increased rainfall between August and September 2022, after which the water level receded to the baseline. We defined baseline as a low water level that persisted for about 15 days. The observed baseline water levels were consistent with 1D analytic solutions that show an increase in water level with increasing distance from the shoreline. This is corroborated by an increase in tidal amplitude as the shoreline distance decreases. The numerical models then confirmed a mean annual variability of about 1m over three decades, except for a period of extreme weather conditions.

This variability is significant enough to cause impairment of septic systems at least twice a year in about 83% of the wells, and this trend increases in simulations using a detrended tide and future rainfall scenarios associated with temperature increases. The water tables did not rise further when rainfall rates were increased beyond the 1.5°C scenario of rainfall, signifying a topography-limited mode in about 83% of the wells. However, 17% of the wells exhibited recharge-limited situations where water levels increased progressively by about 10% at 2°C and 4°C scenarios of rainfall. No correlation was found between the percentage risk of impairment and distance from the shoreline, but the risk correlated with the accommodation space, defined as the difference between water level baseline and surface elevation. This relationship allows the extrapolation of point data from wells in a GIS framework to create a risk map.

The results of this study will help in understanding other coastal processes that are affected by groundwater flow, including salt marsh migration, ghost forests, and coastal flooding, and improve coastal resilience as well as adaptation.